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In search of the sublime Villanueva and the central university campus in Caracas

vidual and collective, mingling with the tropical vegetation and heading towards sublimity. Nowadays, when we revisit the spaces of the Central University campus, we are obliged to ask ourselves if it is possible to perpetuate so many notable achievements. Why should it be so difficult to preserve this eminently successful search for the sublime?

Silvia Hernández de Lasala, was born in Margarita Island. She studied architecture at the Universidad Central de Venezuela, where she also received her doctorate with the dissertation: *En busca de lo sublime. Villanueva y la Ciudad Universitaria de Caracas*. She is the author of several books and she is also, at the present, an Associate Professor at the same University.

Abstract

Throughout his career Carlos Raul Villanueva pursued a dream of integration and synthesis. He wanted to fuse the two different worlds to which he belonged: the enlightened world of European culture and the American world, exotic and provincial but full of that hybrid and tropical attraction which the sensibility of the foreigner in his own country catches better than anyone else. Both worlds were of equal value to him. The desire for integration and synthesis which drove Villanueva on, implied a complex process because European architectonic culture in the first half of the twentieth century by no means constituted a monolithic block, while that of the Americas was largely composed of a mixture of contrasting traditions. What to choose? How to create that particular alchemy which would yield aesthetically significant results, authentic architectonic jewels? The persistent search for an ideal of synthesis led Villanueva, after many explorations, to an approximation to the sublime, an encounter with a foretold American space which paid its respects both to the art and architectonic ideas of the European vanguard and to the creations of artists from Venezuela and other Latin American countries. This new setting, atmospheric and inspiring, full of memories and avant-gardism, bringing together all that was irreconcilable at the time, was constructed by local labor working alongside the experienced artisans which the European wars had blessed with, and our young engineers who were absorbing new techniques with acute creativity. Villanueva dreamed up his own mestizo discourse. ambiguous and complex, indi-